

Development and Evaluation of Chitosan-Based Transdermal Patches for Sustained Co-Release of Curcumin and Berberine

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Received: Nov 20, 2025

Accepted: Dec 03, 2025

Published: Dec 17, 2025

ABSTRACT:

In this study, we developed a matrix-type transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) that incorporates curcumin and berberine, aiming to enhance bioavailability, provide sustained drug release, and improve patient compliance. The system was evaluated for its anti-breast cancer efficacy against the MCF-7 cell line, and an in vitro drug release study was conducted, highlighting its potential as a viable therapeutic strategy. Here, the solvent casting technique is used to develop transdermal patches. The weight uniformity, thickness, drug content, folding endurance, loss of drying, moisture uptake, percentage moisture loss, FTIR, MTT assay, and in vitro drug release are evaluated on transdermal patches. The transdermal patch (F8) exhibits significant anti-breast cancer activity, with an IC₅₀ value of 26.33 µg/mL against the MCF-7 cell line. All patches exhibit good integrity, flexibility, and consistent drug distribution. Formulation F8 shows prolonged drug release, with 98.99% of curcumin and 81.93% of berberine released over 300 minutes. Kinetic analysis revealed that curcumin exhibited zero-order release, while berberine demonstrated zero-order kinetics in formulations F1 and F8, and first-order kinetics in the remaining formulations. The results indicate that the transdermal delivery of curcumin and berberine presents a promising strategy for achieving controlled drug release over an extended duration.

Keywords: Transdermal patches, Curcumin, Berberine, Chitosan, anticancer activity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer (BC) ranks among the most common cancers affecting women, characterized by the malignant growth of breast tissue [1–3]. As of 2020, BC has surpassed lung cancer to become the most commonly diagnosed and fatal cancer in women globally [4]. Breast cancer is diverse and screened into subtypes- luminal A, luminal B, HER2-enriched, and triple-negative- according to molecular biomarkers, namely ER, PR, HER2, and Ki67 [1,5]. All subtypes currently are treated with surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy; however, many patients experience resistance, relapse, and side effects [4]. Oral and intravenous drug administration frequently decreases bioavailability and increases systemic toxicity and patient discomfort. Patch delivery of drugs transdermally mitigates those shortcomings by providing controlled and non-invasive drug delivery with little adverse effects and better patient compliance [6].

Transdermal drug delivery (TDD) is an effective method for drug administration that carries drugs into systemic circulation via the skin without causing irritation [7]. Advantages of TDD include: it is painless, easy to apply, it is a stable drug delivery, reducing side effects and pre-systemic metabolism as in oral delivery [8,9]. Ideally, drugs for TDD would have a molecular weight of ~500 Da and a log P of 1-3 [10]. Due to the stratum corneum limiting penetration, passive delivery devices alter the structure of the stratum corneum to facilitate drug delivery either via swelling or by rupturing the skin. Active delivery devices like microneedles or lasers create a force to facilitate penetration [8,11]. Unlike chemical drugs that are prone to resistance and harmful side effects, natural products provide a safer and multi-target therapy.

Deacetylation of chitin leads to the formation of chitosan. Its molecular makeup comprises amino, acetamido, and hydroxyl groups, which can be altered, activated, and coupled in various ways, which enhances its biological applicability. Chitosan is a natural polymer that carries a positive charge. It is highly modified, allowing it to interact effectively with negatively charged membranes and facilitate movement across them. [11].

The *Curcuma longa* plant serves as the source for producing the compound curcumin (1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadiene 3,5-dione). It has also been shown to possess antioxidant effects, along with an ability to suppress cell proliferation and induce apoptosis [12]. In breast tumors, curcumin opposes angiogenesis by blocking pro-angiogenic VEGF secretion that was induced by osteopontin or medroxyprogesterone acetate. It also modifies the cytoplasmic position of $\alpha\beta4$ -receptor, which inhibits $\alpha\beta4$ signaling and severs inter-receptor exchanges, including those mediated by EGFR and Akt [13]. The nanostructured chitosan matrices help improve curcumin's stabilization and penetration through the skin [14]. At the same time, chitosan patches provide for the therapeutic levels to be maintained in the body for some time thereafter [15].

Berberine, an isoquinoline alkaloid, has shown notable anticancer effects through various mechanisms. Studies have indicated its capacity to affect critical signaling pathways, including AMPK, p53, and NF- κ B, which are essential for the proliferation and survival of cancer cells [16]. Formulating berberine with chitosan improves skin permeation due to the penetration-enhancing property of chitosan [17]. While combining curcumin and

berberine, synergistic chemopreventive effects can be produced by triggering caspase-dependent apoptosis and autophagic cell death through the ERK and JNK/Beclin1/Bcl-2 pathways in MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells [18].

This study developed transdermal composite films combining chitosan with curcumin, berberine, and polymer composites. The films were assessed for several parameters, and *in vitro* drug release and kinetics were performed, along with cytotoxicity evaluations using the MTT assay on MCF-7 cells.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Chemicals and reagents

Curcumin, berberine, chitosan, DMSO, PVP (Polyvinylpyrrolidone), Propylene glycol, and Ethyl cellulose with a 99% purity are used. The MCF-7 cell line was procured from NCCS.

B. Formulation of a transdermal patch

Matrix-type transdermal patches incorporating curcumin and berberine were developed utilizing the solvent-casting technique [19]. Chitosan, with a deacetylation degree of 80%, was dissolved in a 1% glacial acetic acid solution and cast into 8 cm stainless steel rings placed on a glass plate. Propylene glycol served as a plasticizer while varying concentrations of PVP were employed as permeation enhancers. An adequate quantity of the active ingredients was added to the mixture to ensure that each patch contained 10 mg of curcumin and 10 mg of berberine. The solution was then poured onto the glass plate, covered with an inverted funnel, and allowed to evaporate for 24 hours under ambient conditions. Once dried, the patches were wrapped in aluminum foil and stored in desiccators.

C. Characterization of Transdermal Patches

- 1) **Morphological properties:** Patches were assessed by visual inspection, focusing on attributes such as color, flexibility, and smoothness [20].
- 2) **Weight variation and thickness:** Weight variation was assessed by individually weighing the three patches from each formulation using an electronic balance (Shimadzu), followed by the calculation of the mean and standard deviation. The thickness of the transdermal patches was measured at three distinct locations with a digital vernier caliper, and the average thickness was documented. The experiments were carried out in triplicate, and average values were reported [19].
- 3) **Drug content:** The uniformity of drug content in Curcumin and Berberine patches was assessed by homogenizing the patches in 100 mL of phosphate buffer at pH 7.4. A magnetic stirrer was employed to facilitate the dissolution of the patches. Following appropriate dilution, the solution was filtered using a

0.45 μm Whatman filter paper. The drug concentrations were measured at wavelengths of 344 nm and 424 nm, using a UV spectrophotometer [21].

- 4) **Folding endurance test:** The folding endurance test for the prepared patches was conducted manually. This involved repeatedly folding the patch at the same location until it fractured. The folding endurance value was determined by counting the number of folds the curcumin and berberine patches could withstand before breaking [20]. This assessment indicates the effectiveness of the plasticizer and the overall strength of the patches.
- 5) **Moisture Uptake:** The films were precisely measured and stored in a desiccator maintained at a relative humidity of 75%, achieved through a saturated sodium chloride solution. After 24 hours, the patches were weighed again, and the percentage of moisture absorption was determined using the formula below [22].

$$\% \text{ Moisture Uptake} = \frac{\text{Final Weight} - \text{Initial Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

- 6) **Percentage moisture loss:** Three patches from each formulation were precisely weighed and stored in a desiccator with fused anhydrous calcium chloride. After a period of 72 hours, the patches were taken out and weighed again with accuracy. The average percentage of moisture loss for the three patches was then determined [23]. The percentage of moisture loss was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Moisture Loss} = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

D. Evaluation study of transdermal patches

- 1) **Construction of Calibration Standard Curve of Curcumin and Berberine:** 40 mg of curcumin powder was dissolved in 100 ml of methanol to create a stock solution with a concentration of 400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. This stock solution was then diluted by a pH 7.4 buffer solution to obtain a concentration ranging from 2 to 14 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The absorption of each concentration at a wavelength of 424 nm was recorded and used to construct a calibration curve showing the relationship between concentration (x-axis) and absorbance (y-axis). The intercept (a), slope (b), and correlation coefficient (r²) were determined using the linear equation ($y = bx + a$).

A total of 40 mg of berberine powder was dissolved in 100 ml of a buffer solution with a pH of 7.4 to create a stock solution with a concentration of 400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. After, this stock solution was diluted using the same 7.4 pH buffer to obtain concentrations ranging from 0.8 to 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The absorbance of each diluted solution was measured at the maximum wavelength of 266 nm, and these values were used to construct a calibration curve. This method was slightly modified from the work of Prasad V Kadam et al., 2018 [24].

E. Fourier transform infrared spectrometry (FT-IR)

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy is an important method used to analyze the chemical composition and structure of a sample [25] and is used to identify the functional groups present in the transdermal patch. The transdermal patch was examined within the spectral range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using an FTIR spectrometer.

F. In vitro Drug Release Studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted using a Franz diffusion cell, which has a receptor compartment with a capacity of 25 mL. A cellulose acetate membrane was working to facilitate the measurement of drug release from the transdermal patches. This membrane, featuring a pore size of 0.45 μm , was placed between the donor and receptor compartments of the Franz diffusion cell. A transdermal patch containing curcumin and berberine was placed on the cellulose acetate membrane and covered with aluminum foil. The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer at pH 7.4. The entire assembly was secured on a hot plate magnetic stirrer, where constant stir in the receptor compartment was maintained using magnetic beads. Since the temperature of healthy human skin typically remains around 32°C, the diffusion system was kept within a range of 32±0.5°C. Samples were withdrawn from the diffusion cell at various time intervals and analyzed for drug content spectrophotometrically at 424 nm for curcumin and 266 nm for berberine. After each sample withdrawal, the receptor compartment was refilled with an equal volume of phosphate buffer [26].

G. Drug release kinetics

In order to analyze the release kinetics of transdermal patches, four kinetic models were evaluated to establish their fit to the experimental data: zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Hixson–Crowell models. Zero-order kinetics represents an optimal drug release profile characterized by sustained pharmacological effects, as the drug release is considered independent of concentration, with a consistent amount of drug being released over time (Eq. 1)

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0t \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq (1)}$$

The first-order kinetic model characterizes a concentration-dependent release from a system. Essentially, the rate of drug release is proportional to the concentration of the drug in the system, leading to a decrease in the amount released over time (Eq. 2)

$$\ln Q_t = \ln Q_0 + K_0t \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq (2)}$$

The Higuchi model describes drug release behavior as a diffusion process governed by Fick's law, which is influenced by the square root of time (Eq. 3) [27]

$$Q_t = K_H t^{1/2} \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq (3)}$$

The drug release mechanism was examined using the Korsmeyer–Peppas model (log cumulative percent drug release versus log time) to determine if the drug diffusion follows a non-Fickian or Fickian pattern. This kinetic model can be expressed by (Eq. 4) [28]

$$\ln Q = n \ln t + \ln k_p \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq (4)}$$

In this context, Q represents the cumulative percentages of curcumin and berberine released, while k_0 , k_1 , k_H , and k_p are the rate constants related to the release of curcumin and berberine according to the Zero-order, First-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas models, respectively.

H. Cytotoxic activity

The *in-vitro* MTT assay was used to analysis of the cytotoxicity on MCF-7 cell lines. The NADPH-dependent oxidoreductase enzymes are used to measure cell viability, which converts the tetrazolium dye into an insoluble purple formazan product [29]. The MCF-7 cells were first seeded in 96-well plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The cells were washed with the help of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) then the cells were inoculated with or without the final drug concentrations. After 48 hours of incubation, the culture medium was removed. The MTT solution was added to the plate and incubated for 4 hours in a CO₂ incubator under dark conditions. 100 µL of dimethyl sulfoxide was introduced into each well and gently shaken for 15 minutes to dissolve the formazan crystals. A 540 nm wavelength is used to measure the absorbance to determine the cell viability. The percentage of viability was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Viability} = \frac{\text{Sample abs}}{\text{control abs}} \times 100$$

III. RESULTS

A. Formulation of a transdermal patch

Well-structured, smooth transdermal patches containing curcumin and berberine were successfully developed. To enhance the drug's permeation through the skin and maintain the flexibility of the patch, chitosan, propylene glycol, and PVP were incorporated. The study evaluates the patches by assessing their physical and chemical characteristics, analyzing their structure using FTIR, and employing various methods to determine their stability over time. The formulation details of the transdermal patches are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1 FORMULATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES CONTAINING CURCUMIN & BERBERINE

Formulation ID	Curcumin (mg)	Berberine (mg)	Chitosan (mg)	PVP(mg)	PG (%)
F1	10	10	400	300	10
F2	10	10	200	300	5
F3	10	10	200	300	10
F4	10	10	200	100	5
F5	10	10	400	100	10
F6	10	10	400	100	5
F7	10	10	200	100	10
F8	10	10	400	300	5

B. Characterization evaluation

Figure 1, Tables 2 and 3 illustrate the various physicochemical characteristics of the developed transdermal patches. The combination of Chitosan with curcumin and berberine confirmed desirable properties for patch formation, and the film casting technique was successful in producing high-quality patches.

The organoleptic evaluation of all transdermal patches shows that formulations F1, F2, F4, F5, and F7 exhibited a pale color, whereas F3, F6, and F8 were characterized by a dark color. Each patch displayed a smooth surface texture and was opaque. The weight of the transdermal patches varied between 0.33g and 0.74g. The thickness of all patches varied between 0.29 mm and 0.32 mm. Studies on drug content uniformity established a high level of drug content across all formulations, with curcumin levels ranging from 96.62% to 99.1% and berberine levels from 98.2% to 100.7%. The folding endurance tests revealed that all patches possessed good flexibility, with results ranging from 252 to 403 folds. The loss on drying analysis yielded values between 1.42% and 4.86%, while moisture uptake studies indicated a range of 3.48% to 7.07%.

TABLE 2 ORGANOLEPTIC ASSESSMENTS OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

S. No	Physical appearance	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1.	Color	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	Dark yellow	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	Dark yellow	Pale yellow	Pale yellow
2.	Surface texture	Smooth							
3.	Transparency	Opaque							

Figure 1: Transdermal patch: A) Pre-Drying, and B) Post-Drying stages.

TABLE 3 CHARACTERIZATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

Formulation ID	Drug content uniformity (%)		Thickness (mm)	Weight variation (g)	Folding endurance	Loss on drying (%)	Moisture uptake (%)
	CUR	BER					
F1	97.2	98.2	0.31	0.74	312	4.65 ± 2.23	7.07 ± 1.53
F2	99.0	100.2	0.30	0.53	290	2.47 ± 2.09	4.98 ± 1.53
F3	98.4	99.5	0.30	0.54	294	2.81 ± 2.81	5.12 ± 1.32
F4	96.6	98.9	0.29	0.33	252	1.42 ± 2.18	4.48 ± 1.12
F5	98.3	99.6	0.33	0.54	305	3.98 ± 2.06	6.36 ± 0.25
F6	98.5	99.8	0.30	0.53	300	3.37 ± 1.16	5.43 ± 1.16
F7	98.7	100.7	0.31	0.35	275	2.54 ± 1.78	3.48 ± 2.12
F8	99.1	98.7	0.32	0.73	403	4.86 ± 1.16	6.96 ± 0.52

C. Calibration Curve of Curcumin and Berberine

The UV spectra of curcumin and berberine and the absorption maxima were determined by using UV-Visible spectroscopy. The spectroscopy spectra are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: UV Spectra of A) curcumin and B) berberine.

The calibration of curcumin and berberine is essential for determining the kinetic model of our transdermal patch, as the y-values obtained from their calibration are utilized in the mathematical calculation for the kinetic modeling study. Calibration curves were produced by plotting the absorbance against concentration. The linear regression equations establish that, for curcumin, the equation is $y = 0.082x$, and for berberine, it is $y = 0.025x$, where 'y' denotes absorbance and 'x' indicates concentration in $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The concentration range was 2.96 – 14.81 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for curcumin and 0.8 – 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for berberine. This method confirmed linearity within these concentration ranges, in accord with Beer's law. The correlation coefficients (r^2) were determined to be 0.998 for curcumin and 0.994 for berberine, reflecting the excellent linearity of the developed method. The calibration curves for curcumin and berberine are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Calibration curve of A) curcumin, B) Berberine.

D. FTIR analysis

The functional groups of various organic compounds were identified using FTIR spectroscopy, which was conducted over a range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} for this analysis.

The FTIR spectrum of Curcumin reveals a peak at 3492.79 cm^{-1} , attributed to the stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group. The stretching of the SP² C-H bond is indicated by a peak at 2940.94 cm^{-1} . Additionally, a small peak at 1625.99 cm^{-1} corresponds to the conjugation of the carbonyl bond (C=O) with two aromatic rings, while the C=C benzene stretching within the ring is observed at 1601.10 cm^{-1} . A peak at 1487.69 cm^{-1} is due to C-H bending vibrations, and another peak at 1372.17 cm^{-1} is associated with CH₃ bending vibrations. The C-O stretching vibration is noted at 1275.16 cm^{-1} , and the C-O-C bond in the aromatic ring shows a peak at 1023.89 cm^{-1} . Finally, a peak at 854.50 cm^{-1} is attributed to C-H aromatic hydrogen.

In the case of berberine, the FTIR spectrum displays an N-H stretch peak at 3321.12 cm^{-1} , while the C-H stretch of the aromatic ring is indicated by a peak at 3048.67 cm^{-1} . The C-H stretch of alkenes appears at 2946.27 cm^{-1} , and the C-C stretch in the aromatic ring is observed at 1597.82 cm^{-1} . Peaks at 1567 cm^{-1} and 1504 cm^{-1} are due to C=C bending, with C-H bending peaks at 1388.63 cm^{-1} and 1330.94 cm^{-1} . The C-O stretch and C-N stretch in aromatic amines are represented by peaks at 1270.62 cm^{-1} and 1227.56 cm^{-1} , respectively, while C-O-C bending is noted at 1104.28 cm^{-1} .

The FTIR spectrum of the transdermal patch and chitosan exhibits nearly identical peaks, differing by only 2 or 3 cm^{-1} . A peak at 3312.99 cm^{-1} likely indicates the stretching vibration of the O-H bond, while aliphatic C-H stretching is represented by bands at 2933.20 cm^{-1} and 2880 cm^{-1} . The C=O bond is characterized by a peak at 1654.31 cm^{-1} . Additionally, a peak at 1569.34 cm^{-1} corresponds to N-H bending, and C-O stretching is observed at 1378.36 cm^{-1} and 1331.45 cm^{-1} . The C-O-C bond is identified by a peak at 1077.53 cm^{-1} . All of these FTIR spectra are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: FTIR Spectra of Berberine, Curcumin, Chitosan, and Transdermal Patch.

E. *In Vitro* Drug Release Studies

The cumulative release of curcumin and berberine from eight different transdermal patches was investigated under *in vitro* conditions utilizing an artificial semipermeable membrane. The drug release profiles for formulations F1 to F8 confirmed that curcumin was released at rates of approximately 97.04%, 99.62%, 99.69%, 99.17%, 97.32%, 98.88%, 99.60%, and 98.99% at 300 minutes. Similarly, the release rates for berberine were found to be 81.61%, 77.89%, 79.06%, 76.02%, 80.56%, 79.68%, 76.74%, and 81.93% at the same time point. A detailed analysis of the drug release is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Cumulative percentage of drug release for A) Curcumin and B) Berberine

F. Drug Release Pattern Analysis

The *in vitro* drug release data from formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, and F8 undergo a complete analysis using various kinetic models, including zero-order, first-order, the Higuchi model, and the Korsmeyer-Peppas model. The result of our study indicates that all the transdermal patches F1-F8 show a zero-order model towards curcumin, like that of F1 and F8 transdermal patches show a zero-order model towards berberine; the remaining transdermal patches show a first-order model towards berberine. Our findings indicated that the zero-order model and first-order model best describe the release profiles for curcumin and berberine, as confirmed by the coefficient of determination (r^2) values obtained. For curcumin, the r^2 values for the zero-order model were very high for all formulations: 0.9884 for F1, 0.9764 for F2, 0.9824 for F3, 0.9688 for F4, 0.9901 for F5, 0.9864 for F6, 0.9751 for F7, and 0.9911 for F8. Similarly, the release of berberine shows a strong correlation with zero-order and first-order models, with r^2 values of 0.9549 for F1, 0.9616 for F2, 0.9568 for F3, 0.9765 for F4, 0.9528 for F5, 0.9553 for F6, 0.9692 for F7, and 0.9603 for F8. All the details are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4 KINETICS PARAMETERS OF CURCUMIN AND BERBERINE RELEASE FROM DIFFERENT TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

Formulation	Zero-order (r^2)		First-order (r^2)		Higuchi-order (r^2)		Korsmeyer-Peppas model (r^2)	
	Curcumin	Berberine	Curcumin	Berberine	Curcumin	Berberine	Curcumin	Berberine
F1	0.9884	0.9549	0.7548	0.9486	0.8492	0.9396	0.5702	0.8131
F2	0.9764	0.9378	0.6526	0.9616	0.9144	0.9481	0.4806	0.8396
F3	0.9824	0.9419	0.6431	0.9568	0.906	0.9457	0.4705	0.8307
F4	0.9688	0.9205	0.7163	0.9765	0.9244	0.9645	0.5395	0.8711
F5	0.9901	0.9515	0.7848	0.9528	0.8724	0.9418	0.5984	0.821
F6	0.9864	0.9419	0.7382	0.9553	0.9043	0.9459	0.5572	0.828
F7	0.9751	0.929	0.6583	0.9692	0.9155	0.9563	0.4855	0.8555
F8	0.9911	0.9603	0.6802	0.9424	0.8962	0.9315	0.4997	0.8021

G. Cytotoxic activity

The anticancer and cytotoxic effects of the transdermal patch (F8) were assessed using the MCF-7 cell line. Various concentrations of the patch were incubated with MCF-7 cells for 48 hours in a CO₂ incubator, and the selectivity index was determined based on the IC₅₀ value. Doxorubicin was used as the standard drug for comparison.

To evaluate the inhibitory effects on cancer cells, different concentrations (3.12, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50, and 100 µL/mL) of both the transdermal patch (F8) and doxorubicin were incubated with the MCF-7 cell line for 48 hours. The results showed that increasing the concentration of the transdermal patch (F8) and doxorubicin led to a decrease in cell viability. The IC₅₀ values for the transdermal patch (F8) and doxorubicin were determined to be 26.33 µg/mL and 9.32 µg/mL, respectively, after 24 hours of treatment. The results are shown in Figures 6 and 7. The MTT assay results of this study showed that the transdermal patch (F8) was effective against the MCF-7 cell line.

MTT Assay

Figure 6: Cytotoxicity of Transdermal Patches Against MCF-7.

A) F8 TRANSDERMAL PATCH

B) DOXORUBICIN (Positive Control)

Figure 7: MTT assay for Anticancer activity on MCF-7 A) F8 transdermal batches, and B) Doxorubicin.

IV. DISCUSSION

The physical characteristics of the transdermal patches differed based on the different amounts of chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol. Patches F1, F2, F4, F5, and F7 exhibited a pale appearance, and F3, F6, and F8 were darker in color. The thickness of the patches varied between 0.29 and 0.33 mm, with these differences connected with the viscosity of the polymers and the rate of solvent evaporation.

The patch weights were different due to varying concentrations of chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol. The lowest amount of polymer was used in formulation F4 (0.33g), and the highest amount in formulation F1 (0.74g). Each patch has 10 mg of curcumin and berberine; the weight differences were attributed to polymer composition, which affects patch thickness, folding endurance, moisture absorption, and drying loss. F4 exhibited the least value of folding endurance (252) because of the low concentration of PVP, which is a plasticizer, while F8 showed the maximum value (403) with increased PVP concentration.

The lowest loss on drying was observed at F4 (1.42%), following indicates that the lowest levels of chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol were used. The low drying loss was attributed to the low hydrophilic and hygroscopic properties of these constituents, as well as curcumin and propylene glycol. The hydrophilic and

hygroscopic nature of chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol has been reported in [30–32]. F8, on the other hand, had the maximum loss on drying (4.86%) due to the high concentrations of chitosan, polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and propylene glycol that increased moisture absorption.

In the moisture absorption analysis, formulation F1 shows the greatest capacity for moisture absorption from the environment may be caused by its high levels of propylene glycol, PVP, and chitosan. In contrast, formulation F7 exhibited less moisture uptake, which may be due to its low concentrations of these ingredients. Under optimal conditions, the absorption spectra of curcumin and berberine were analyzed using a pH 7.4 buffer solution as a blank reference. The absorption spectrum of curcumin exposed two different peaks, one at 424 nm and another at 220 nm. The peak at 424 nm corresponds to the π to π^* transition of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond, which aligns with findings from previous studies that reported a peak at 420 nm [33]. The peak at 220 nm represents the presence of iron impurities in the extract [34]. In the case of berberine, multiple peaks were recognized. Strong bands were observed around 250 nm and 350 nm due to π to π^* transitions, while a weaker band was noted at 430 nm [35].

The calibration curve for curcumin discovered a linear relationship within the concentration range of 2.96 to 14.81 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which aligns closely with findings from another study linearity was noted within the range of 2 to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [36]. Similarly, the calibration curve for berberine established a linear relationship in the range of 0.8 to 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [37].

FTIR analysis confirmed the structural integrity of chitosan present in the patch, suggesting successful polymer integration. No peak shifts indicated physical trapping of both curcumin and berberine, as peaks were characteristic and compared with stick spectra. The broadening or shifts around 3400 cm^{-1} suggested hydrogen bonding between chitosan and both drugs [38]. While spectra for curcumin, berberine, and chitosan are in close agreement with the results from previous studies [39–44]

The assessment of drug release profiles across various formulations indicated that F8 is the most promising option for transdermal delivery. *In vitro* release studies have shown that F8 possesses a well-defined release profile characterized by several beneficial phases. During the initial phase, F8 shows a release of 14.41% curcumin and 19.80% berberine, both active pharmaceutical ingredients, within the first 30 minutes, indicating its ability for rapid therapeutic onset. This was succeeded by an intermediate phase, achieving a cumulative release of up to 54% at 180 minutes, and ultimately approaching nearly complete drug release at 99% by the 300-minute mark. The triphasic release pattern of F8 efficiently balances burst and controlled delivery mechanisms. This release profile is mainly advantageous in reducing the frequency of dosing and minimizing side effects related to concentration fluctuations. The observed triphasic release pattern may be attributed to the large amounts of chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol present in the F8 formulation. The increased levels of these components likely enhance the matrix structure and facilitate the entrapment of drugs within it, which leads to a sustained release. F8's release characteristics are well-suited for treatments that are necessary for stable drug effects over time, providing a rapid onset coupled with prolonged action, thus making it an excellent candidate for transdermal drug delivery.

The rapid release noted in the early stages of incubation may be due to the dissociation of weakly bound curcumin molecules on the surface of the polymer capsules or from curcumin particles that were not fully encapsulated by PVP. This phenomenon could be relevant to our transdermal patches, allowing for the rapid release of poorly bound drugs such as curcumin and berberine. The zero-order release model represents drug release that is unchanged by concentration, while first-order kinetics denote a direct relationship between drug release and concentration. The Korsmeyer-Peppas model illustrates the relationship between log cumulative percentage of drugs released and log time. Our analysis indicates that the transdermal patches mainly follow the zero-order model for curcumin and the zero-order and first-order models for berberine. According to the Korsmeyer-Peppas model, the slope values for all eight formulations of transdermal patches ranged from 0.5 to 0.89, indicating that the release mechanism is characterized by non-Fickian diffusion.

The transdermal patch (F8) was subjected to a study of the anticancer and cytotoxic effects against the MCF-7 cell line, respectively. We have found good anticancer activity in our study with a better selective index. In our study, we found that the transdermal patch (F8) has good anticancer activity with an IC₅₀ of 26.33 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. In various studies, curcumin and berberine have already been reported for their anticancer activity. 40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of curcumin shows a percentage inhibition of 64.00% against the MCF-7 cell line [29]. In the Kazemi-Lomedasht et al., study, curcumin has an IC₅₀ value of 22 μM against the T47D breast cancer cell line [45]. 25 μM of berberine shows 41% and 63% cell growth inhibition against the MCF-7 cell line in the incubation period of 24 hrs and 72 hrs [46].

The transition from the G2 phase to the M phase of the cell cycle was prevented by the curcumin, by suppressing the expression of cdc2/cyclin B [47]. Curcumin causes cell death via caspase-3 activation and it stimulates the GADD153, which leads to the promoter of apoptosis [48]. Moreover, it activates the pro-apoptotic members of the Bcl-2 family, like Bax, and it inhibits the anti-apoptotic genes like Bcl-XL [49], increases the level of p53, Bax, and procaspase-3, -8, and -9 [50]. The anticancer activity of berberine hydrochloride has received significant attention due to its ability to interact with nucleic acids. It binds to specific DNA sequences and inhibits telomerase and topoisomerase, leading to stabilizing structures like DNA triplexes and G-quadruplexes, which contribute to inhibiting cancer cell growth [49,51].

V. CONCLUSION

This research successfully developed and evaluated a matrix-type transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) that incorporates curcumin and berberine, using chitosan, PVP, and propylene glycol as important excipients. The formulation exhibited improved mechanical strength, flexibility, and consistent drug distribution, making it suitable for transdermal use. In-vitro drug release tests of the transdermal patch (F8) show a sustained and controlled release pattern. Kinetic analysis reveals that curcumin shows zero-order kinetics, whereas the berberine F1 and F8 show zero-order kinetics, and the remaining transdermal patches show first-order kinetics. Additionally, cytotoxicity evaluation against the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line shows significant anticancer effects, with F8 showing an IC₅₀ value of 26.33 µg/mL. This study establishes a basis for further *in vivo* studies for a new herbal-based transdermal patch in cancer treatment.

Acknowledgments

The corresponding author gratefully acknowledges Dr. Suresh Rathinasamy for his valuable methodology support and for permitting the cytotoxicity study to be conducted in his laboratory at the Department of New Drug Discovery, Greensmed Labs, Chennai – 600097, Tamil Nadu, India.

Author contributions

A.S.B. and J.P. were primarily responsible for writing the draft of the manuscript, developing and optimizing the experimental methods, and conducting data collection and analysis. V.S.P. and G.V. contributed to the conceptualization and design of the study, prepared the figures and tables. S.R. supervised the entire project, provided essential oversight, and ensured the manuscript met publication standards. All authors contributed to editing, visualization, and validation of the manuscript, and all authors have approved the final version. The authors confirm that no paper mills or artificial intelligence were used.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding

We sincerely appreciate PANNAI Charitable and Educational Trust support and encouragement extended to the researchers in our research project, which allowed us to successfully complete this research project.

Ethical considerations

Not applicable

Data availability

All source data for this work (or generated in this study) are available upon reasonable request.

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